

STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING OF CEMENT BASED MATERIALS REINFORCED WITH GRAPHENE NANOPATELETS

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ABSTRACT

The present work focuses on the use of graphene nanoplatelets for the development of smart cement based nanocomposites that, contrary to traditional approaches that require the use of high-cost attached sensors, can themselves be used as damage sensors of structural components. Three different types of exfoliated graphene nanoplatelets (xGnP), having the same thickness (6-8 nm) but different diameter, ranging from 5 to 25 μm , were used. Initially, the effects of different xGnP concentrations on the electrical resistivity of cement paste were investigated with the objective to define the nanoplatelet's percolation threshold. Based on those results, the nanoreinforced composites that exhibit the lowest resistivity per each xGnP type were subjected to compressive cyclic loading-unloading in the nanocomposite's elastic region. During the experiment their electrical resistance was simultaneously recorded in order to investigate their piezoresistive properties and self-sensing ability. It was found that the xGnPs addition reduces the electrical resistivity of the matrix and gives the piezoresistive ability to the cementitious material so that the mechanical response of the nanocomposite can be effectively monitored. It was observed that the larger the xGnPs diameter the higher the electrical resistance change is, which indicates a better screening of the applied mechanical stress during testing.

1 INTRODUCTION

The majority of the infrastructure nowadays is constructed and repaired using different types of cement based materials, due to their low cost and easy handling. Despite their worldwide use, however, cement based materials are sensitive/susceptible to cracking. Current technologies to monitor the integrity of a structure usually involve high-cost attached or embedded sensors that are application specific and provide information on particular locations of the structure. The implementation of these sensors is often limited by the size of the sensors and sometimes, especially in the case of the embedded sensors, downgrades the material's mechanical performance. Present demands for safer infrastructure dictate the development of novel and innovative materials that will exhibit additional functions such as the capability to monitor their structural integrity.

In order to achieve this goal, this study focuses on the development of smart cement based nanocomposites reinforced with graphene nanoplatelets that themselves can be used as strain/stress sensors. Graphene is the newest and most advantageous nanoscale material for reinforcement. Due to its extremely high stiffness (Young's modulus of 1 TPa) and ultimate strength (130 GPa), single-layer graphene has been established as the strongest material ever measured [1]. Moreover, it has a very high electrical conductivity [2, 3]. Additionally, its electrical properties are independent of the chirality which makes graphene a promising material for the development of sensors and high-performance nanoelectronics.

To date, research efforts have been concentrated on successfully developing graphene/polymer composites with sensing capabilities [4, 5]. To our knowledge research on the potential of using graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) as sensors in cementitious matrices is limited. Initially, Sedaghat et al [6] studied the electrical resistivity of cement nanocomposites reinforced with 1 vol%, 5 vol% and 10

vol% graphene nanoplatelets. The results have shown that the addition of graphene substantially decreases the resistivity of the cementitious matrix. Following, Pang et al [7] investigated the sensing capability of mortar specimens with GNPs under both cyclic and monotonic compressive and tensile strain and found that the cement/GNPs nanocomposites have the potential to be used as sensors. More recently, Le et al [8] studied the damage sensing capability of mortar samples with graphene nanoplatelets at high concentrations (1.2 %, 2.4 %, 3.6 % and 4.8 % by volume of the material). Using the four-probe set-up, the electric potential across prismatic specimens with a known notch depth was measured and the results were compared with finite element simulations. No mechanical load was applied. It was demonstrated that as the GNP amount exceeds a percolation threshold value (around 2.4 vol%), the electrical conductivity of the GNP-infused mortar is insensitive to the moisture content, which makes it a reliable damage-sensing material for infrastructure applications.

In the present work, cement based nanocomposites incorporating graphene nanoplatelets were developed. The matrix was reinforced using three different types of exfoliated graphene nanoplatelets (xGnP). The xGNPs had a thickness of 6 to 8 nm and diameters of 5, 15 and 25 μm , respectively. Initially, the electrical resistivity of cement paste reinforced with the different xGnP types at various concentrations was investigated. The objective was to define the nanoplatelet's percolation threshold according to the nanoplatelets' diameter. Following, the nanoreinforced composites that exhibit the lowest resistivity, per each xGnP type, were subjected to compressive loading-unloading in the nanocomposite's elastic region while their electrical resistance was simultaneously measured, in order to investigate their piezoresistive properties and self-sensing ability. The results indicate that xGNPs can be efficiently used to monitor the structural health of cement based materials.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 Materials

The xGnP/cement nanocomposites were prepared using Type I ordinary Portland cement and Grade M graphene nanoplatelets supplied by XG sciences Inc, Michigan. The xGNPs had an average thickness of approximately 6–8 nm, a typical surface area of 120 to 150 m^2/g and average particle diameters of 5, 15 or 25 microns. To facilitate with the xGNPs dispersion in water a polycarboxylate based high range water reducer admixture provided by Sika (Viscocrete Ferro 1000) was used.

2.2 Preparation of the xGnP/cement nanocomposites

Prior to mixing with the cement powder, the xGNPs were dispersed in an aqueous solution that contained the water reducer admixture. Seven different dispersions were prepared for each xGnP diameter that corresponded to concentrations of 0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3 and 0.4 % by weight of cement. To homogeneous disperse the xGNPs in the above solution ultrasonic energy was applied using a probe ultrasonicator. Typically, a method, similar to the aforementioned one, is utilized to disperse nanoscale materials for use in the cementitious matrix. However, the suspensions prepared by this way have a high aqueous content of 98.68%, which usually corresponds to the mixing water [9]. This impedes their wide use in practical applications. Therefore, in this study the xGNPs were dispersed in less than one third of the mixing water. Independent of the xGNPs concentration the proportions of the water/admixture/xGnP suspensions per volume were kept constant at approximately 70 vol%, 28.3 vol% and 1.7 vol%, respectively, to make certain that the nanoplatelets were dispersed in a similar manner in all the different suspensions.

After dispersion, extra water was added to the suspensions that corresponded to a water to cement ratio of 0.3. The resulting mixture was hand stirred and mixed with the cement using a standard mixer according to ASTM C305. Following, the cement paste nanocomposites were placed in prismatic $20 \times 20 \times 80$ mm molds. The specimens were demolded after one day and were placed in water saturated with lime until the age of 28 days. Prior to testing, the samples were placed in an oven at a temperature of 80 ± 1 °C to dry for 72 hours. Minimum of three specimens were prepared for each case.

2.3 Test method

The electrical resistivity of the nanocomposites was measured using the four wire method. During casting, four steel electrodes were embedded into the samples covering the entire cross-section of the specimens (Fig. 1a). The distance between the outer and inner electrodes was 15 mm and the space between the inner electrodes was 30 mm.

Figure 1: (a) Specimen with steel electrodes immediately after casting and (b) experimental test set up for electrical resistance measurement.

A Keysight multimeter was used to make the four wire ohm measurements (Fig. 1b). The inner electrodes were used to measure the voltage and the outer electrodes to supply the current. The electrical resistance was recorded every 3 seconds for a period of 30 minutes to eliminate any electrical polarization effects. After testing, the electrical resistivity of the nanocomposites was calculated using the following equation:

$$\rho = R(A/l) \quad (1)$$

where R is the electrical resistance of the specimen, A is the cross-section and l the distance between the inner electrodes.

The piezoresistive characteristics of the nanocomposites were investigated by measuring the electrical resistance of the samples and simultaneously applying several compressive loading and unloading cycles. The load was applied using a 10 kN MTS testing machine at a constant displacement rate of 0.2 mm/min. A maximum load of 2.3 kN, which corresponds to a 6 MPa stress, which is in the elastic region of the material, was applied. The load and the electrical resistance were recorded during testing. The experimental setup is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Photograph showing the specimen with attached cabling during the piezoresistivity test.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to determine the optimum concentration of the exfoliated graphene nanoplatelets the electrical resistivity of the nanocomposites was investigated. The results of the three different xGnP types are shown in Figure 3. It is observed that all the nanocomposites, regardless of the nanoplatelets type and concentration, demonstrate lower resistivity compared to plain cement paste. This was expected as the addition of a conductive reinforcement should decrease the resistance of the matrix. Looking at the results of the graphene nanoplatelets having a diameter of 5 micron (5 μm xGnPs) it is observed that the samples with a concentration of 0,1 wt% xGnPs demonstrate the lowest resistivity. Compared to plain cement paste the resistivity is decreased approximately 70%. The composites with lower or higher amounts of xGnPs exhibit higher resistivity. In the case of 15 microns (15 μm xGnPs) the nanocomposites with amounts of 0.05, 0.1 and 0.15 wt% of cement xGnPs show similar resistivity with the samples with 0.15% to exhibit the smallest standard deviation. Similar to the results of the 15 microns, the optimum concentration for the nanoplatelets with a diameter of 25 micron (25 μm xGnPs) is close to 0.15 wt% of cement.

Figure 3: Effect of xGnPs concentration on the electrical resistivity of nanocomposites reinforced with (a) 5 micron, (b) 15 micron and (c) 25 micron nanoplatelets.

According to the electrical resistivity results, the composites that demonstrated the lowest resistivity, i.e. the samples with 5 micron xGnPs at an amount of 0.1 wt% of cement and the samples with 15 and 25 microns xGnPs at a concentration of 0.15 wt% of cement, were subjected to several loading-unloading cycles under compression. During the experiment the load and the electrical resistance were simultaneously recorded. The maximum stress applied was 6 MPa so as to be in the nanocomposite's elastic region. The results are shown in Figure 4. The black line corresponds to the applied stress and the blue line demonstrates the fractional change in the resistance. It can be seen that in all cases the nanocomposites demonstrate a piezoresistive behavior, the electrical resistance of the samples is changing according to the applied stress, which indicates that they can be used as sensors. Comparing the results of the nanocomposites, it is observed that the samples reinforced with xGnPs having a diameter of 5 microns exhibit a 2% change in resistance, which is the lowest. For the composites with xGnPs having a diameter of 15 microns the fractional change in resistance is doubled reaching 4%. The best results, which correspond to the highest fractional change in resistance (up to 6.5 %), are obtained by the 25 micron nanocomposites. Therefore it can be concluded that the larger the xGnPs diameter the higher the electrical resistance change is, which indicates a better screening of the applied mechanical stress during testing.

Figure 4: Piezoresistive response of cement nanocomposites reinforce with (a) 5 micron xGnPs at a concentration of 0.1 wt% of cement, (b) 15 micron xGnPs at a concentration of 0.15 wt% of cement and (c) 25 micron xGnPs at a concentration of 0.15 wt% of cement.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The development of smart cement based materials with exfoliated graphene nanoplatelets for structural health monitoring was studied. The xGnPs addition was found to decrease the resistivity of the matrix. The optimal concentration of xGnPs with a small size (average diameter of 5 μm) was found to be around 0.1 wt% of cement. In the case of xGnPs with a larger diameter (average diameter of 25 μm) a slightly higher concentration, around 0.15 wt% of cement, appeared to be optimum. The investigation of the piezoresistive characteristics of selected nanocomposites, that demonstrated the lowest resistivity per each xGnP type, has shown that xGnPs are promising nanomaterials for the development of smart cementitious nanocomposites for structural health monitoring. In particular, a better screening of the applied mechanical stress, i.e. a higher fractional change in resistance, is observed when xGnPs with a larger diameter are used.

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